

NATO Defense College

Vox Collegii

The voice of the College

Applying the NATO / Partnership for Peace Consortium Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum in an Increasingly Interconnected Landscape
Dinos A. Kerigan-Kyrou

The GCC and Maritime Security:
between Cooperation
and Competition
Giulia Daga

NATO Approaches 70:
an Existential Reflection
Christopher De Marco

NATO's Effective Multilateralism:
the Means to Counter Hybrid Threats
Maria Elena Argano

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Christopher De Marco, in his article, gives us some valuable current insights on the role and relevance of NATO in an age of rapid change. In the last article, the importance of NATO's effective multilateralism — its ability to interact with other international actors in order to prevent and solve challenges, especially in countering hybrid threats arising from a multilateral order — is examined. As an example of this process of adapting its strategies and structures, in 2016, NATO started a regular cooperation with the EU, to counter the hybrid threats which posed a danger to the security of both institutions.

guidelines, collected into "Recommendations for Canada's G7 Presidency", crucial for a wider gender equality environment among the G7 countries.

In keeping with tradition, the NATO Defense College successfully delivered the 7th edition of the Senior Executive Regional Conference (SERC) and the 19th NATO Regional Cooperation Course (NRCC), which represent two of the most significant examples of outreach and engagement towards members and partners, alongside Senior Course 132, the flagship course of the College.

Dear Reader,

In this editorial, I would like to introduce you to the latest edition of *Vox Collegii*, a cornerstone of our institution. In the next few pages, you will find an in-depth analysis of topics, such as cyber and maritime security, NATO's effective multilateralism, and newly developed technologies in the field of military aviation.

In the first of the articles, Prof Kerigan-Kyrou describes how cybersecurity is increasingly becoming central to every aspect of our lives. For this reason, the Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum adopts a holistic, multidisciplinary approach to the domain; from basic cyber awareness to sophisticated training within complex networked environments.

The second topic is the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC): in the article the author explains how a common maritime security strategy is far from being achievable, because of maritime border disputes, historical distrust and differing political objectives. As a result, NATO has followed a bilateral approach, with the establishment of Individual Partnership and Cooperation Programmes (ICCP), with Kuwait in 2014 and the UAE in 2016.

Over the last six months, the NATO Defense College has continued to develop its three key missions, with a special and particular focus on outreach activities. Many initiatives have been enhanced, with the participation of the Commandant who has played a key role in external activities such as the Conference of Commandants, held in Zagreb; the Riga StratCom Dialogue 2018; and the last edition of the G7 held in Canada, where she was a member of the Gender Equality Advisory Council. The Council prepares fundamental

In accordance with the 5 main areas of activity agreed at the NATO Heads of State and Government summit in July 2018, the NDC programme continues its work for the benefit of the Alliance on defence and deterrence, projecting stability, NATO-EU cooperation, adaptation, and the fight against terrorism.

Dear Reader,

Much has happened and has been accomplished at the NDC since the previous issue of *Vox Collegii*. Not only have we continued to be successful in carrying out our main missions, but we have also continued with the physical improvements to our facilities; and made progress mapping our institution's future in order to maintain relevance for NATO and its partners.

The NRCC (NATO Regional Cooperation Course), a key part of our outreach programme, saw 45 Course Members from 18 countries graduate from the 19th iteration of the Course, of which nine (20%) were civilians and diplomats. Since its inception in 2009, over 560 participants have graduated from the Course.

Generals, Flag Officers and Ambassadors' Course (GFOAC) 2018-1 was held from 11 to 15 June and was again a resounding success. So, too, was the Senior Executive Regional Conference, the seventh of its kind, which saw 29 high-ranking military officers and civilian equivalents from 17 countries interact over a week in early May. Five Modular Short Courses (MSC) were also held during the last Senior Course (SC).

As for SC 132, 74 Course Members representing 30 NATO and partner nations

have concluded a journey that provided them with better insight and perspective, not only on NATO, but on the world at large. The graduates have now acquired the status of "Anciens" of the NDC, and can in turn spread the word on the value of the knowledge and the significance of the networks built up while at the College.

Since February, our Research Division has continued to organize and sponsor multiple conferences and events, while publishing yet another book and 10 research papers. It also hosted visiting scholars and research fellows. The Research Division also provided support for the educational mission of the College by providing mentors, Senior Flag Officers, and reviewers for all the Study Projects and Individual Papers produced by Senior Course Members. On 1st May, Dr Thierry Tardy took over from Dr Jeff Larsen as Head of the Research Division.

Over the last year, the College has pursued its outreach activities, with significant progress achieved in relations with other defence educational institutions from around the world. In fact, this year's Conference of Commandants, hosted in Zagreb by the Croatian National Defence Academy, saw the largest number of participants in its history.

To update you on the progress of the NDC's Strategic Plan — to ensure a well-considered and robust product — we have continued to engage both internally with staff and the leadership of the NDC, as well as externally with the Military Committee, the NATO Defence Manpower Committee, our Academic Advisory Boards, and some Permanent Representatives to NATO. We are grateful for the generous feedback we have received as we chart the NDC's path into the future.

We were given authority by NATO HQ to enter into a trial that will test the initial conclusions made about the NDC structure, as well as the in-depth analysis achieved through the

mapping of our business processes. The start point for the trial has been provided to nations through NATO HQ. The key result is for the NDC to continue providing excellent service to the Alliance, while ensuring we do so in a way that is both effective and reflects the good stewardship of the resources entrusted to us. We need to preserve our unique contribution to the Alliance: a one-of-a-kind blend of NATO-based education, research and outreach that takes place in a multi-national environment with multi-national staff, helping to develop skills in consensus-building, strategic thinking and critical analysis for senior officers and civilian officials from NATO and partner nations, to prepare them for service in an international security environment.

I take this opportunity to thank our departing members and wish them all the best in their future endeavours, be it further employment or well-deserved retirement. Your contribution to the NDC has not gone unnoticed, and was instrumental in making the NDC a finer institution. Of particular note, I would like to recognize the extensive contribution made by Ms Anne Dupont, who was the backbone of the NDC for over 24 years, and by Brigadier General Heinz-Josef Feldmann, Director Academic Planning and Policy Division (DAPP), to whom we are indebted for his leadership over the past 4 years.

In closing, I should like to formally welcome Dr Thierry Tardy to the Research Division, and Brigadier General Rolf Wagner, from the German Armed Forces, our new DAPP. I also welcome the Course Members of SC133 and NRCC 20, as they start their own journey toward expanding their knowledge, leadership and communication skills, but most importantly, as they perfect the art of reaching consensus.

Lieutenant-General Chris Whitecross
Royal Canadian Air Force
NDC Commandant

Applying the NATO / Partnership for Peace Consortium Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum in an Increasingly Interconnected Landscape

Dr Dinos Anthony Kerigan-Kyrou

Dr Dinos Anthony Kerigan-Kyrou is a member of the Emerging Security Challenges Working Group at the Partnership for Peace Consortium (PfPC). He is a co-author of the NATO / PfPC Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum. Dinos is a visiting lecturer at the University of Greenwich, and is a cybersecurity instructor on the NATO DEEP (Defence Education Enhancement Programme). He is responsible for cybersecurity within the Senior Command & Staff Course at the Defence Forces of Ireland.

The opinions expressed in this article are his own and must not be attributed to the NATO Defense College or to the North Atlantic Treaty Organization.

The NATO Cybersecurity Curriculum is a generic reference programme applicable to a wide range of government, military, and commercial activity.¹ It is based around themes crucial to the application of cybersecurity for military and other organisations. This paper will look at how NATO and Partner Nations can apply the Curriculum to a rapidly changing and interconnected cyberspace environment. Firstly let us review what we understand by the concept of cybersecurity.

Cybersecurity affects each and every person in every organisation - whether that organisation is military or civilian. Cybersecurity is increasingly becoming central to every aspect of our lives. Cybersecurity is the protection of our personal, organisational, and governmental information from unauthorised access and control. For example, good cybersecurity ensures our data and information is secure, whether that data belongs to an individual, a business, or a government. It is essential for keeping Intellectual Property and Research and Development safe from espionage. Cybersecurity is key to securing our connected critical infrastructure - our telecommunications, energy, water, and transport. And cybersecurity is vital for defending NATO and Partner Nations' security.²

The Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum adopts a holistic, multidisciplinary approach to cybersecurity. The authors used the phrase 'generic' quite deliberately; the Cybersecurity Curriculum can be applied by any civilian or military organisation. It can be applied to all levels of training; from basic cyber awareness to sophisticated training within complex networked environments. To achieve this generic format with such a wide applicability the team responsible for the Curriculum created four guidance frameworks, or 'themes'.

The first theme, 'Cyberspace and the Fundamentals of Cybersecurity', identifies the structural components of cyberspace - the networked environment in which computers and interconnected devices communicate.

The second theme, 'Risk Vectors of Cybersecurity', examines cybersecurity weaknesses created by increased risk. Vulnerabilities can be exploited by nefarious actors including criminals, terrorists, and hostile states. Understanding such dangers is an essential component of cybersecurity risk assessment and mitigation. Moreover, it helps to create a stable and resilient cybersecurity environment.

1) The Partnership for Peace Consortium (PfPC) Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum is endorsed by Allied Command Transformation as a NATO Educational Reference Document. It was developed by the PfPC's Emerging Security Challenges Working Group and led by Dr Detlef Puhl of NATO's Emerging Security Challenges Division, Dr Michael Hennessy of the Royal Military College of Canada, and Prof Sean Costigan of the Marshall Center. It is available to download from the NATO website at: www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/pdf_2016_10/20161025_1610-cybersecurity-curriculum.pdf (Or search for: NATO Cybersecurity Curriculum.)

2) See also: Costigan, Sean and Perry, Jake, ed. (2012), *Cyberspaces and Global Affairs*, Routledge.

https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/pdf_2016_10/1610-cybersecurity-curriculum.pdf

The third theme, 'International Cybersecurity Organizations, Policies and Standards', looks at the increasing importance of standards and the development of a cybersecurity legal framework. The speed and advancement of technology have largely outpaced the development of laws and verifiable standards; nonetheless, international and national standards are slowly being developed and are likely to take an ever greater role in the development of robust cybersecurity procedures and practice.

The fourth theme, 'Cybersecurity Management in the National Context', explores some of the key issues for national authorities to consider when devising new cybersecurity laws and regulations. Such issues include how technology is managed, with the identification of cybersecurity vulnerabilities and threats, managing cybersecurity incidents, maintaining situational awareness of the cybersecurity environment, and the ability to manage change. Such change is continual and cybersecurity training needs to be adaptable to new and ever developing circumstances and technology.

One of the biggest challenges facing NATO and Partner Nations is the cybersecurity of what is known as the Internet of Things (IoT). The four themes of the Curriculum are ideal for application to this new environment.

The IoT consists of internet devices (or 'things'), receiving and transmitting data. These devices contain sensors and actuators able to perform critical functions. Most of these devices are, in effect, computers running software and 'firmware' (a computer program stored within the hardware).

The IoT enables huge advancements in NATO and Partner Nations' capabilities. But it may also create increased vulnerabilities; these vulnerabilities are a key, yet often overlooked part of the cybersecurity challenge we face.

For example, United States Navy Rear Admiral Paul F. Thomas states that the maritime environment is increasingly dependent on integrated digital systems on-board US vessels.³ This is equally true on land, in the air, in space, and at sea. Indeed a previous edition of this Journal correctly identified cyber as a 'fifth domain'.⁴ As Dr Elena Mandalenakis states: "Cyber systems are globalized, inter-connected and highly integrated." This fact exacerbates any disruption in a local system with "unforeseen risks and consequences."⁵ Dr Mandalenakis highlights the example of the US Arleigh Burke-class destroyer, first deployed in 1991 with a crew of 329, and the Zumwalt-class, deployed in 2013 with a crew of only 158, but with a tenfold increase in defence capabilities. The Zumwalt-class is, however, totally reliant on electronic, integrated systems for its military abilities and operational systems.⁶

The success of NATO operations depends increasingly on the security of cyberspace and the Internet of Things. The internet is the backbone of this interconnection. Contrary to popular

3) *RADM Paul F. Thomas, US Coast Guard. Evidence to: 'Protecting Maritime Facilities in the 21st Century'. Hearing before the Subcommittee on Border and Maritime Security, US House of Representatives, October 8, 2015. Serial No. 114-35, p.43.*

4) *See: De Vivo, Diana (2014) 'NATO Enhanced Policy on Cyber Defence: Towards the Wales Summit 2014' in, Vox Collegii, Vol IX, pp. 16-20.*

5) *Mandalenakis, Elena (2016), University of Peloponnese: "Political Implications of Cyber Space on State Power," NMIOTC - Maritime Interdiction Operations Journal, 13, no.2: pp. 15-24; Available at: www.kenap.mil.gr/files/NMIOTCjournal13.pdf*

6) *ibid.*

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https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_78170.htm

belief there is no 'separate' internet for critical infrastructure such as energy, communications, or transport. Likewise, there is no separate internet for the military environment. As the US Dept of Defense (DoD) stated in 2016:

"...the immense promise of this technology comes with immense risks...Now, with such capabilities being given Internet access, DoD is entering a quickly deepening pool of vulnerability. At risk are all the things that embrace the Internet of Things: DoD facilities, equipment, employees, and their possessions – any of which could be used to cause harm. We could soon be in a position where a determined adversary could shut down our power and water, turn off our security systems, disrupt our ability to provide medical care, listen to our conversations, and monitor our movements. If the Department does not take action to get

ahead of this problem, it will get exponentially worse, and the rise of IoT could immerse DoD like a tidal wave."

Dr Stefan Lüders of CERN, the European Organization for Nuclear Research, states that 32% of CERN's IoT devices (used for power, security, and research) either crashed or failed when faced with the most basic vulnerability scan.⁸ Indeed Dr Lüders confirmed to the author, in regard to the security situation of IoT devices: "I think it is just getting worse."⁹ As NATO and Partners progress toward an environment consisting of the Internet of Things, the

7) 'US Dept of Defense Policy Recommendations for The Internet of Things (IoT)' December 2016. Available at the website of the DOD Chief Information Officer: <http://dodcio.defense.gov/Portals/0/Documents/Announcement/DoD%20Policy%20Recommendations%20for%20Internet%20of%20Things%20-%20White%20Paper.pdf?ver=2017-01-26-152811-440>

8) Dr. Stefan Lüders, CERN. Presentation at the ITU; available at: [www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/com17/Documents/tutorials/2012/11CERNComputerandGridSecurityITU\(2012\).pdf](http://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/com17/Documents/tutorials/2012/11CERNComputerandGridSecurityITU(2012).pdf)

9) Email to the author from Dr. Stefan Lüders, CERN, August 31, 2017.

<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Cybersecurity.png>

suppliers of these components and devices may need to play a much greater role in ensuring their products' security.¹⁰

Dr Lüders points out that there is presently no device standard or verification system for IoT.¹¹ Until one is developed the author proposes that the standard for Information Security Management Systems (ISO 27001:2013; identified in Theme 3 of the Cybersecurity Curriculum), is used as a guideline to verify software, control systems, and the multiple IoT devices that we increasingly depend upon.¹² Closer collaboration between NATO's Emerging Security Challenges Division,¹³ the Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence¹⁴, the NATO Communications and Information Agency,¹⁵ the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA, based in Heraklion and Athens),¹⁶ and EU Europol's EC3 (cybersecurity division)¹⁷ will become increasingly important. While 100% security can never be guaranteed, both NATO and the EU may need to exert greater influence on device suppliers to ensure the robustness and resilience of components. Finally, improving cybersecurity information sharing (as identified

in the fourth theme of the Curriculum) will greatly help. Indeed, the United States has developed an excellent platform for sharing cybersecurity threats and challenges – the US Computer Emergency Readiness Team (US-CERT).¹⁸ Likewise, the EU's 'Network and Information Systems Directive'¹⁹ will compel critical infrastructure operators to share cybersecurity breach information, and that information in turn can be shared between the EU and NATO.

Collaboration and information sharing are central to the Curriculum. They are critical for the identification of cybersecurity challenges, in exactly the same way that they are for the identification of terrorist and other asymmetric threats. Indeed, it was the 9/11 Commission Report which first highlighted the vital importance of collaboration and information sharing to identify and disrupt emerging threats at the earliest possible opportunity.²⁰

Likewise, in aviation there is a 'Just Safety Culture' where the reporting of errors is encouraged and honest mistakes are not punished, thereby allowing everyone to learn, according to Comdt Frank Byrne of the Irish Defence Forces.²¹ Moreover, Comdt Byrne writes that this approach cannot be taken for granted; it has to be continually maintained with constant effort

¹⁰ Freely available software, through the Open Vulnerability Assessment System (OpenVAS), includes 'Metasploit' vulnerability scanning and 'Kali Linux' penetration testing software to test the robustness and resilience of IoT products. For more information see: www.metasploit.com and www.kali.org

¹¹ Dr Lüders, Presentation at the ITU, op.cit.

¹² ISO: International Standards Organization. This is known as a Second Party Audit, or 'an audit on suppliers'.

¹³ See: <https://esc>

¹⁴ See: www.ccdcoe.org

¹⁵ See: www.ncia.nato.int

¹⁶ See: www.enisa.europa.eu, especially: www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/iot-and-smart-infrastructures

¹⁷ See: www.europol.europa.eu/about-europol/european-cybercrime-centre-ec3

¹⁸ See: www.us-cert.gov

¹⁹ EU 'Directive on Network and Information Systems, 2016'. See: www.ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/network-and-information-security-nis-directive

²⁰ See: Chapter 13 'How to Do It? A Different Way of Organizing the Government'; 9/11 Commission Report, available at: www.9-11commission.gov/report/911Report.pdf

²¹ Byrne, Frank (2017) 'The Journey Towards a Just Culture in the Irish Air Corps' in, Defence Forces Review XI p.199; available at: http://www.military.ie/fileadmin/user_upload/images/Info_Centre/documents/Annual_Reviews/Defence_Forces_Review_2017.pdf

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and engagement to demonstrate and promote the Just Safety Culture. Cybersecurity should be no different to aviation. It is the approach taken within aviation that we can all learn from to protect cyberspace.²²

Furthermore, the idea of physical barriers no longer applies in cyberspace. As Prof Edward Amoroso states: "Toronto is vulnerable if Australia gets hit."²³ The vast distance between the countries makes no difference whatsoever in cyberspace. This is why it is so important that the Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum can be applied to all military and civilian organisations for cybersecurity training at every level. The Curriculum is highly adaptable to new technology and to new circumstances, particularly our rapidly and increasingly interconnected environment. As Major General Stefano Vito Salamida states, on behalf of Supreme Allied Commander Transformation:

"I am convinced that it can serve as a reference for partner countries in the design and development of course models and programmes for professional Cybersecurity military education. It will also serve as an enhancement of military interoperability between NATO and its partners and strengthen the collaboration on a responsive education and training system. It is my pleasure to support the PfPC Emerging Security Challenges Working Group through publishing this Cybersecurity Reference Curriculum as a NATO document."²⁴

At its core, ensuring effective cybersecurity should be extremely simple. It is about the early identification of problems – recognising them when they are 'small' before they become 'big' – and then dealing with these challenges in a resilient way. Achieving this is less a technical matter and more about management, people and process. Cybersecurity requires information sharing; organisations need to work holistically (rather than in traditional 'silos'), empowering each and every person with a shared responsibility to identify cybersecurity problems. Cybersecurity is no longer a matter solely for the Information Technology (IT) team. While the IT departments will continue to remain important, identification of problems is a responsibility concerning every individual; not a single employee or contractor now has a role that can be considered separate from cybersecurity. It is crucial that all civilian and military personnel are able to identify cybersecurity concerns

as early as possible in a 'no blame' environment, in order that problems are identified and dealt with as early as possible. This new, holistic approach to how we manage cybersecurity, which is encapsulated in the Curriculum, is vital for military and non-military environments within the NATO Alliance and across NATO Partner Nations.

²² Kerigan-Kyrou, Dinos A. 'Critical Infrastructure: Cybersecurity and Organization'; presented at the 'Critical Infrastructure Resilience Conference, UK Security Expo', London, November 2016.

²³ Prof Edward Amoroso, New York University School of Engineering, '9th Cyber Security Lecture Sponsored by AIG, November 16, 2017; available at: www.youtube.com/watch?v=3x_6m9BcxX8&t=1883s

²⁴ Cybersecurity Generic Reference Curriculum, op.cit, p.4.

The GCC and maritime security: between cooperation and competition

Giulia Daga

Giulia Daga is currently a trainee at Frontex in the Operational Response Division, where she is mainly involved in Maritime Affairs and Coast Guard cooperation.

After a master's degree in International and Diplomatic Sciences, in 2017 she graduated in Strategic Studies and International Security at the Ca' Foscari University and the Naval Staff College of Venice.

She then continued cooperating with the Naval Staff College with an internship as Operational Planning Process Teaching Assistant.

Specialising in Maritime Strategy with a thesis on sea control and sea denial in the Persian Gulf, she deepened her knowledge of the Middle East thanks to a year at the Institute of Oriental Languages and Civilisations (INALCO) in Paris.

The opinions expressed in this article are her own and must not be attributed to the NATO Defense College or to the North Atlantic Treaty Organization.

Since the establishment of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) in 1981, its member states¹ have developed different visions about the role the organization should have in the security field. The very first sign of a possible common security dimension was the establishment of the combined Peninsula Shield Force in 1982 – implemented in 1986 – which was composed of 5,000 soldiers and based in Saudi Arabia. However, in 1990, Peninsula Shield remained inoperative during the Iraqi invasion of Kuwait, showing the limits of the organization's freedom of action in the military domain. In 2000, the GCC took further steps forward with the signature of the Joint Defence Agreement, a NATO Article 5-like pact which established that an attack on any GCC country would signify an attack on them all. During the 2011 upheavals in Bahrain, intervention was requested for the first time by the Al Khalifa family, even if the role of the Peninsula Shield Force was limited to protecting key infrastructure.

In the meantime, doubts about Peninsula Shield's effectiveness were raised by Oman in 2005, when, after the fall of the Baathist regime in Iraq, its usefulness seemed ended. However, Saudi Arabia strongly supported the idea of widening and strengthening the force, fostering the creation of a Rapid Intervention Force in 2009, then backing the idea of a Unified Military Command and an Anti-Missile Shield during GCC summits in 2012 and 2013. The increase in the total number of forces and the creation of new structures, however, have not led to any concrete improvement in the effectiveness of the mechanism. The main problem is still the lack of a common defence strategy, resulting from differing objectives and a relevant degree of distrust. As a result, the institution has never released a strategic concept or performed along those lines, proving that the GCC's security cooperation still remains largely symbolic.²

1. The US and NATO security approach to the region

The United States clearly recognized the lack of a coherent GCC defence structure, and have developed bilateral security agreements with individual countries, since the start of direct US involvement in the Gulf in the 1990s. They signed Defence Cooperation Agreements with Kuwait and Bahrain in 1991, with Qatar in 1992 (updated in 2013), and with the UAE in 1994. Also, Bahrain and Kuwait (in 2002 and 2004) obtained Major non-NATO Ally Status, which meant they could benefit from more sophisticated US arms purchases.³ Saudi Arabia and Oman signed no Defence Cooperation Agreement, but they have hosted hundreds of US military personnel under less formal partnerships.

1) Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Oman, Qatar, Kuwait and Bahrain.

2) Alajmi Zafer M. (2015), *Gulf Military Cooperation: tangible gains or limited results?* Al Jazeera Centre for Studies: Doha; Saïdy B. (2014), *GCC's Defence Cooperation: moving towards unity*, Foreign Policy Research Institute: Philadelphia, PA; Gaub F. (2016), *An Arab NATO in the Making? Middle Eastern Military Cooperation since 2011*, The Letort Papers, Strategic Studies Institute, US Army War College: Carlisle, PA, p. xii.

3) *Despite this upgrade, the United States has decided to keep an "Israeli qualitative military edge" over any Arab country in their arms sales*; Katzman K. (2015) *The Gulf Cooperation Council Camp David Summit: Any Results?*, Statement Before Subcommittee on the Middle East and North Africa, Congressional Research Service: Washington DC, pp. 7-8.

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NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg welcomed the Secretary General of the Gulf Cooperation Council, Abdul Latif Bin Rashid Al Zayani to NATO headquarters
https://www.google.it/search?biw=1920&bih=934&tbm=isch&sa=1&ei=VnQOW7KnKMWwsAG7x6nICA&q=stoltenberg+gulf+state&oq=stoltenberg+gulf+state&gs_l=img.3...8799.15455.0.16398.26.24.2.0.0.102.2018.21j3.24.0...0...1c.1.64.img..0.14.1218...0j0i67k1j0i30k1j0i10i24k1j0i19k1j0i30i19k1j0i8i30k1j0i5i30k1.0.KDgzJaN6iFY#imgrc=GCSAUzLF9DpfmM:&spfl=1527673960393

At the same time, however, after the complexities raised by post-2003 Iraq, the GCC countries started to officially denounce US actions. The main dilemma for the Arab Gulf countries is that American presence is vital to their survival, yet it is the main source of discontent that leads to the rise of fundamentalist groups. To cope with these challenges, the majority of GCC countries have opted for an increasingly diversified security approach, involving European and Asian partners.

In particular, Saudi Arabia has made efforts to diversify its arms import sources, slightly increasing acquisitions from the PRC, while continuing its Western imports, in particular from France, the UK, Canada and Germany. The UAE did the same, adding Russia, Sweden, Italy and Turkey to the list of its main arms suppliers.⁴ In the field of security partnerships, India has played an increasing role, by signing defence cooperation agreements with the UAE in 2003, with Oman in 2005 and Qatar in 2008, while upgrading its relations with Saudi Arabia into a strategic partnership in 2010.⁵

Another important part of this diversification process is GCC countries' cooperation with NATO. Bahrain, Qatar, Kuwait and

the UAE joined NATO's Istanbul Cooperation Initiative in 2004. The Initiative was also a response to NATO's goal to expand out-of-area partnerships, in line with the 1999 Strategic Concept,⁶ and was launched during a NATO summit in Istanbul. The ICI was open to all the countries in the region which had an interest in cooperating, according to a vision that linked the stability interests of the Gulf region with that of the Euro-Atlantic area, given the economic relations between the two. The main focus of the ICI has been the fight against terrorism and WMD proliferation. The most relevant outcomes of this cooperation were the military contributions made by Bahrain and the UAE to ISAF and the provision of air assets to Operation Unified Protector in Libya by Qatar and the UAE in 2011, the same year in which for the first time an Emirati Ambassador was appointed to NATO.⁷ However, the main obstacle to further developing the initiative was the non-adherence of Saudi Arabia and Oman, whose combined 70% share of GCC countries' military expenditure implies a considerable weakness in the ICI's effectiveness.⁸

4) Cordesman Anthony H. and Peacock M. (2015) op. cit., p. 41; SIPRI Arms Transfers Databases, Stockholm International Peace Research Institute: www.sipri-org/databases.

5) Ulrichsen K. C. (2015) *Insecure Gulf: The End of Certainty and the Transition to the Post-Oil Era*, Oxford University Press: New York, pp. 38-39; Pradhan P. K. (2011) *India's Defence Diplomacy in the Gulf*, Institute for Defence Studies and Analyses (IDSA): New Delhi

6) *The Alliance's Strategic Concept (April 21, 1999) Press Release NAC-S (99) 65*, North Atlantic Treaty Organization: Brussels.

7) *The Istanbul Cooperation Initiative (April 2014), Fact Sheet, Public Diplomacy Division, North Atlantic Treaty Organization: Brussels; Samaan J.-L. (2014), Putting energy security on the agenda of NATO Gulf Partnership, "Energy Security Forum n°9", NATO Energy Security Centre of Excellence: Vilnius, p. 10.*

8) Kishk Ashraf M. (2009), *The Istanbul Cooperation Initiative Agreement between NATO and the Gulf Cooperation Council Countries: Obstacles and Propositions*, NATO Defence College, Research Division: Rome, p. 20.

FGS Hessen (F 221), right, and USS Forrest Sherman (DDG 98) conduct a strait transit with USS Harry S. Truman (CVN 75).

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/usfleetforcescommand/40904653335/in/photolist-25jB3kH-TeukPH-edDJVQ-efUM3H-stCaPj-TawmG-bKYduZ-a1tVqT-ditgL1-9p68LB-SvrmJV-RVz2qH-TKiJZn-SsLRm5-HAtnzq-r1QyEw-SsKPHs-Jcz1A9-TvkLvF-pFsFmF-pDncGf-7KpuR1-eW4vXp-SvqhMP-W9W9aE-s91nKi-9XqLPW-25jAYs2-e9EJ9k-VyLmut-gLAYMG-f3q1wJ-nudvPY-25H72WL-WT3qGK-cLqgd1-e2SVvZ-4uy4qh-251rtj8-e3vWjF-26543Vj-aqrPYj-W9Wab7-f6AYMB-fmw3ZY-HDqgbw-25AFXqL-X2jpf1-fuTv4V-25mj9V>

One of the main reasons why the two countries chose not to participate in the initiative is that they were the two main sponsors of an evolution of the GCC into a supranational institution, active in the security field. They also both saw the involvement with NATO (which in most of the Gulf populations' perception was seen as too close to the US), and a potential source of internal instability. Moreover, Saudi Arabia did not wish to be placed on the same level as the other small Gulf countries, thus preferring bilateral frameworks. Oman, on the other hand, did not join the ICI because of its historical neutral stance on Gulf security, due mostly to its closer relations with Iran, whose non-involvement in the ICI could have resulted in a cooling of relations between the two countries. However, Omani and Saudi hesitation was not an outright rejection of all

military cooperation, especially in the field of counterterrorism, border security, WMD counter-proliferation, training and information sharing.

As for the countries which decided to adhere to the ICI, they stressed their willingness to do so on a bilateral basis, thus limiting NATO's intention to focus on a multilateral framework approach. The bilateral approach was therefore followed by the Atlantic Alliance with the establishment of Individual Partnership and Cooperation Programmes (IPCP), with Kuwait in 2014 and the UAE in 2016.

Nonetheless, in 2017, some important steps in the development of the ICI were taken, with the establishment of the NATO-

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Istanbul Cooperation Initiative Regional Centre in Kuwait, on January 24. It is indeed an important achievement, because it is the first NATO presence in the Persian Gulf region. Also, Omani representatives and the Secretary General of the Gulf Cooperation Council joined NATO member states and ICI countries after the opening ceremony. The Centre started its activities in September 2017, with a NATO week focused on different issues, including maritime security and crisis management. However, despite its increasing focus on out-of-area involvement, the organization still does not have the desire to get involved more directly. Owing mostly to budgetary considerations, NATO seems to prefer assuming a diplomatic posture in its initiatives, despite the military emphasis given to them.⁹

When it comes to more operational forms of security assistance, the United States continues to keep the lead: 35,000 American troops were stationed in GCC countries in 2015, and the Obama administration accelerated its actions toward regional cooperative security, hosting the US-GCC Camp David Summit on May 14, 2015. Probably organized to reassure GCC countries of American commitment despite US involvement in sponsoring an agreement with Iran, the Summit Joint Statement underlined the importance of developing “collective approaches to regional issues”. In particular, the United States affirmed its intention to stand with its GCC partners in the case of aggression or any threat of aggression – support which would include all appropriate action, including the “potential use of military force”, especially in the maritime domain.¹⁰

Effectively, in case of an escalation in tensions with their main naval rival, Iran, GCC countries would expect a strong US-led intervention, which is why the GCC countries’ navies have focused on coastal assets, developing, in particular, patrol boats, mine countermeasure vessels (MCMV) and anti-missile capabilities. However, recent trends show that GCC countries are increasingly willing to expand their naval assets, though without disputing the American role.¹¹

2. The GCC countries’ maritime security approaches

Saudi Arabia, in particular, has undertaken a Naval Expansion Programme, which aims at making the country able to obtain “regional maritime dominance, maintaining freedom of

navigation while simultaneously repelling aggression”.¹² These objectives are clearly meant to counter Iranian naval power, with the intention of more than doubling naval capabilities from the estimates of 2011-2012. Also, the Saudi Navy held, at the beginning of October 2016, one of its greatest naval drills in the Persian Gulf, Strait of Hormuz and Gulf of Oman area, the “Gulf Shield 1” exercise.¹³ Despite these actions, the Saudi navy has always received fewer resources than the other military services, so that it is still considered mediocre especially in terms of combat readiness.¹⁴

The Omani position is a very interesting one in the Persian Gulf system. Geopolitically, Oman has had a history of turbulence at the border with Yemen, thus identifying stability as one of the core elements of its strategy. At the same time, its long maritime history, with its strategic position on the Strait of Hormuz, has opened the country to commercial relations all around the Indian Ocean, one of the main partners continuing to be Iran. Religiously, Oman is the only country with a majority of Ibadi Muslims in it, Ibadism having remained the only other branch of Islam, apart from the Sunni and Shia traditions.¹⁵

All these aspects concur to make the country unique in the region, and in a perfect position to play a mediating role to foster Persian Gulf stability. In particular, Oman is the only GCC country which did not take part in the Saudi-led campaign against Yemen, thus playing a vital role in ongoing negotiations.¹⁶ Moreover, its relations with Iran have many times brought the country to adopt neutral positions, especially in the maritime domain, since the time of the Iran-Iraq war.¹⁷ The two countries continued to cooperate informally in the field of maritime security until 2010, when they formally signed a security cooperation agreement to counter piracy and smuggling in the Strait of Hormuz and the Gulf of Oman.

Despite its cooperation with Iran in the military field, Oman is highly dependent on Western countries for its national security, and on the United Kingdom, in particular, for advisory positions. Recently, Oman has also increased defence cooperation with

9) Cordesman Anthony H. (2014) *op. cit.*, p. 41.

10) US-GCC Camp David Joint Statement (May 14, 2015), *The White House, Office of the Press Secretary*; Washington DC; Katzman K. (2015) *op. cit.*, p. 6.

11) Cordesman Anthony H. and Peacock M. (2015) *The Arab-US Strategic Partnership and the Changing Security Balance in the Gulf*, Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), Rowman and Littlefield: Lanham-Boulder-New York-London, p. 136.

12) Obaid N. (2014), *A Saudi Arabian Defense Doctrine, Defense & Intelligence Projects*, Harvard Kennedy School, Belfer Center for Science and International Relations: Cambridge, MA, p. 19-29. Obaid N., *op. cit.*, p. 29.

13) Al-Muhlim A. (October 11, 2016), *Gulf Shield 1 showed Saudi preparedness*, Arab News: www.arabnews.com; Shay S. (October 17, 2016), *Saudi Navy conducts Major Exercise in the Gulf*, Israel Defense: www.israeldefense.co.il; Saudi Gulf Shield 1 (October 5, 2016), *Gulf Times*: www.gulf-times.com.

14) Cordesman Anthony H. and Peacock M. (2015), *op. cit.*, pp. 136-138.

15) Kechichian Joseph A. (1995), *Oman and the World, the Emergence of an Independent Foreign Policy*, RAND: Santa Monica, CA, pp. 249-255.

16) Barrett R. (2015) *Oman's Balancing Act in the Yemen Conflict*, Middle East Institute: Washington DC.

17) For example, Oman mediated for the release of 15 British Navy personnel when they were captured by Iranian forces in 2007.

the United States, continuing the old relationship which started with the 1833 treaty and was reinforced through a military cooperation agreement in 1980, then renewed in 2010. This agreement provides the United States with the possibility of using various ports and installations in Masirah, Muscat, Thumrait and Musnanah, the two countries being jointly active in counterterrorism and maritime security in the Strait.¹⁸ Oman offered its facilities during *Operation Enduring Freedom*, and in a lesser way also in *Operation Iraqi Freedom*. However, it has never provided its troops to international coalitions, a trend that it has maintained during the war against the Islamic State in Syria¹⁹ and Iraq.²⁰

The smallest countries in the Gulf region (the UAE, Bahrain, Qatar and Kuwait), which have a limited population for their military needs and have not seen the GCC develop a common military policy, have largely relied on foreign assistance and equipment to provide for their security.²¹ Their military forces have developed thanks to bilateral agreements with international powers, and have recently begun to grow due to considerable increases in military expenditure. At the naval

level, these GCC countries have mainly developed some autonomous capabilities in aspects like patrolling and mine warfare. However, they never conduct their manoeuvres and drills unilaterally, always acting bilaterally with the British, the French or the Americans.²²

3. Conclusions

A GCC common maritime security strategy is far from being achievable. Maritime border disputes, historical distrust and different political objectives prevent GCC countries from having a solid common ground on which to build security cooperation. As a result, the navies of the Gulf Arab countries are all focusing on developing the same kind of assets, without imagining a cooperative strategy with shared competences and instruments. Of course, strengthening GCC security cooperation would free the organization, at least in part, from all the internal and external drawbacks of a persistent foreign presence. However, fostering regional cooperation initiatives to share responsibilities and develop interoperability would require an

overall renunciation of sovereignty that is difficult to imagine.²³ As a result, the only main achievement of recent years has been some progress towards the diversification of foreign security providers, meaning that the countries concerned do not have to rely on a regional security umbrella.

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18) Cordesman Anthony H. (2016), *op. cit.*, p. 198; Cordesman Anthony H. (2014), *op. cit.*, p. 38.

19) Unlike Saudi Arabia, Qatar and the UAE, Oman has no intention to directly intervene in Syria, probably in order to avoid dissent with Iran over the Al-Assad regime.

20) Katzman K., *op. cit.*, pp. 11-14.

21) Krane J. (2014), *Energizing NATO cooperation with the Gulf monarchies: New opportunities under the old energy-for-security paradigm*, "Energy Security Forum n°9", NATO Energy Security Centre of Excellence: Vilnius, p. 15.

22) Legrenzi M., *op. cit.*, p. 77.

23) Al-Kaabi Mohamed K. (2012), *The Strategic Alternatives of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) disruption of maritime traffic in the Arabian Gulf as a result of Iranian threats to close the Strait of Hormuz*, Naval Postgraduate School: Monterey, CA, pp. 66-80.

NATO Approaches 70: An Existential Reflection

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The opinions expressed in this article are his own and must not be attributed to the NATO Defense College or to the North Atlantic Treaty Organization.

At the dawn of NATO's 70th anniversary, there will be much discussion regarding its role and relevance in an age of rapid change. There will also be a tendency to cast a nostalgic view towards the Alliance's past while noting its achievements over the decades. Such reflections are crucial, as they ensure NATO does not lose sight of its heritage while also ensuring that it maintains its transformation from a Cold War persona to a revitalised and more agile institution. In doing so, NATO must also demonstrate that it possesses a reinvigorated mindset and character, one with a depth for strategic creativity and a renewed and progressive vision. These fundamental ways of thinking and envisioning will enable NATO to anticipate, navigate and keep pace with an increasingly opaque spectre of security challenges.

NATO is, above all, a political organisation with a military dimension. As such, the safeguard of consensus will continue to buffer the Alliance from the ambivalent and shifting thresholds of political acceptance while ensuring it meets its core task of collective security. However, Members may also consider the Alliance's role as a global player, a function further enhanced through a widespread network of partnerships. Acceptance of this role requires a conceptual and intellectual shift to recognise that it does not exclusively imply boots-on-the-ground, but, rather, represents an opportunity to reduce intervention through active prevention.

Despite this seemingly tall order, the good news is that NATO is well equipped to meet these challenges. After all, it needs only to reflect on its past in order to maintain momentum for its future.

Stocktaking

Decision-makers, policy developers and enablers alike can take inspiration from the Alliance's sizable history as they set out to shape and implement its future posture.

NATO has been in a near-constant state of evolution since its inception. It is a perpetual 'work-in-progress', prone toward self-reflection, reshaping and adaptation. Consider its commendable 'open-door' membership policy that netted a more than twofold increase from its initial establishment. Further enhancing NATO's core membership strength is the expansive partnership network of state and organisational actors. The highly successful Partnership for Peace programme has enabled the Alliance's enlargement by providing an entry route through which 13 states have gained NATO membership, six of which were former Warsaw Pact members. In this sense, NATO plays a pivotal role as a benchmark for states who purposefully undertake sovereign advances towards more open and democratic societies, dedicated to the rule of law and cooperation within the framework of international norms.

At the fore of NATO's activity is the forward positioning of multinational composite brigades, a display of reassurance and deterrence at NATO's easternmost borders. Similarly, a robust cycle of desktop to simulated battlefield exercises ensures NATO is able to rapidly response to threats emanating from the air, land, maritime and cyber domains.

By the same token, we have witnessed the deployment of Allied forces at NATO's frontiers, and beyond, in active response to humanitarian crises and regional conflicts. Let us not forget the 2001 invocation of Article 5 in defence of the nation whose capital witnessed the signing of the Alliance's namesake treaty. The results of this unanimous response remain in place nearly 17 years on, with Allied sons and daughters having made the greatest of sacrifices.

Behind the scenes, NATO has also sought to bind together its diverse range of internal elements and capabilities into a cohesive whole through a range of efforts. Hence the standardisation of everything from spare parts to ammunition to projects, aimed at ensuring the interoperability of distant radar systems. A premium has also been placed on fiscal foresight, through the promotion of multinational logistics solutions in theatres of operation that yield significant 'economies of scale.'

Now, on the eve of a new decade, NATO must prepare for the potentially turbulent times ahead. In doing so, it must embrace concepts of conceptual creativity and keep pace with innovative developments across the defence and techno-industrial domains while retaining its core values and principles.

Core values

Critics will often cite the more obvious point of contention with respect to NATO's core method of governance, the rule of unanimity. Achieving consensus is surely a time-consuming feat without any guarantee of success. Negotiations may result in diluted bargaining, caveats may exceed the length of actual agreements, and compromise may be a necessary bridge to achieve a functional mandate. Nevertheless, at the end of the discussions, NATO's ultimate strength is that 29 autonomous states can collectively determine a single course of action for the benefit of most, if not all. This remarkable outcome of collective will forms the nexus of NATO's unique character and personality. As such, it remains the responsibility of its Member States to preserve and defend its inviolability.

Going a step further into the character of NATO, one may even observe that it has a tendency to maintain a perpetual state of

existential questioning, that it is an organisation still finding its place. However, closer observation would reveal that this inwardly reflective nature is, in fact, *by design*; a built-in function whose purpose is to ensure NATO engages in a constant dialogue of self-analysis. This questioning nature ensures that NATO keeps a cautious eye on the various benchmarks of relevance and maintains a steady posture of preparedness. Such tendencies do not imply obsolescence, but, rather, affirm its existential relevance by ensuring it remains on-course.

To be sure, the societies that NATO represents today are vastly different from those of its beginnings. The rise of liberalism within the NATO sphere, along with unfettered globalisation, has so transformed the world as to make it nearly unrecognisable from the age of NATO's conception. Nevertheless, the hard-earned advances stemming from the ravages of a world war are contested by internal and external elements alike. Multinational institutions established as a reflection of a common humanity are under threat of dismantling; the rule of law is challenged rather than promoted; coercive force vies with dialogue and diplomacy for the settlement of disputes; and the veracity of an unbiased media outlet is increasingly drawn into question.

Despite these fundamental changes in the global system, the overarching challenges and threats remain the same. Similarly, the wishes, hopes and aspirations of societies, as well as their anxieties and fears, also remain largely unchanged. While the shadow of imminent threat may not be as visible in terms of forward-deployed battalions on standby with artillery and supplies awaiting dispatch to the front lines, the perception and corresponding angst of threat remain just as palpable. There is an existential anxiety within the contemporary world. NATO must respond to this by recalling that it was born in an age of great devastation and sacrifice.

The current scene

In order to effectively deal with the severity of real and perceived threats, NATO must now address how they have not only expanded but also matured and morphed into unimaginable combinations and networks. Viewed independently, the broad swath of issues that NATO confronts may appear innumerable. We must adjust our vision to bring these threats into focus.

An increasingly elusive and far-reaching nemesis, with elements that we have yet to conceive, faces NATO. From rapidly adaptable terrorism to a blurring of the distinction between states and non-state entities, there is a very real and active challenge to the liberal world order whose security NATO helps safeguard.

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On top of this, there is the added trial of addressing ambiguous and ultra-responsive threats that seek to take advantage of NATO's deliberate consultation process. While not appealing to all capitals, pre-emptive operations may be required to offset or neutralise these threats before they gain traction and become irreversibly detrimental. Again, active prevention is preferable to responses which may be too little too late.

We must take into account that technological developments may outpace the Alliance's ability to respond. Consider innovations such as 3D / 4D printing, Artificial Intelligence, semi and fully Autonomous Weapons Systems. In the hands of the most dangerous entities, these tools can be used to devastating consequence.

Furthermore, the question of nuclear threats remains as a looming cloud on the collective security horizon; a threat exacerbated by the likely membership increase in the nuclear club.

Then there are the threats to the non-physical frontiers of NATO societies, namely hybrid warfare coupled with cyber incursions and aggressive misinformation campaigns set at destabilising and casting doubt upon the democratic principles of NATO's societies.

There are also security consequences of environmental degradation, which results in erosion of societal cohesion, mass geographical exodus and threats to energy security. The increasing scarcity of natural resources may have a third-order effect, leading to such dissatisfaction and alienation that terrorism becomes an inviting vehicle to air grievances.

Alongside these emerging and nonconventional threats, we must look at the standard toolkit – Ballistic Missile Defence, Air Defence, Joint Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance – common-funded capabilities whose development can take the better part of 15 years. Given the current security context, there is clearly room for improvement in this area. By supplementing organic capabilities with a broadened partnership with industry, academia and research institutes and think tanks, NATO can gain valuable insight into pioneering research and development and original ways of thinking.

In terms of tools, NATO possesses the most valuable component in the form of its human capital. It can strive to enact balanced recruitment through the recognition of diversity, therefore harnessing as broad a talent base as possible. NATO should also fully recognise the importance of cultivating an empowered staff element that is ready to create innovative strategies in response to non-linear threats.

In addition, the crossroads of military-diplomatic-political efforts should be revisited. For example, the enhancement and harmonisation of EU and NATO forces needs to be a key milestone in the next decade, while ensuring that the autonomy of EU Member States is not diluted and the transatlantic bond remains intact.

Lastly, a more efficient utilisation of resources would help reduce overall institutional waste. Redundancy is a force multiplier, but duplication is disruptive and leads to 'mission creep'. A shift away from the '2%' priority towards a broader perspective that also takes into consideration contributions 'in kind' and 'host nation' should be cultivated. The introduction of economies of scale and outsourcing can further strengthen strained resources, where appropriate.

Looking ahead

At the public level, NATO must reaffirm its role as the solemn guarantor of peace and security for its members – not only within its traditional geographical space but further afield, both

in the physical and non-physical realms. In reaffirming its hard-earned gravitas to the broader global audience, NATO must acknowledge its role and demonstrate its commitment as the promoter and guardian of the socio-political, economic and cultural aspects that comprise the critical vectors of cohesion within the Alliance. These efforts must not be limited to the obvious cycle of exercises and forward deployments, but also include a visible public outreach programme and deliberate engagement with its constituents. Furthermore, in order to be meaningful, these reaffirmations must be tangible, enduring and a measured balance between the pragmatic and the unyielding. The end-state of transformation working in this direction should be strategic coherence across a spectrum of asymmetrical and hybrid threats, resulting in a renewed Strategic Concept for 2020 and beyond.

Therefore, throughout the coming year, let us reflect upon the collective wisdom gained after these many decades and feel confidence in NATO's ability to achieve a revitalised capacity by harnessing the advances within its reach, in order to guarantee the common peace and security that so many have made sacrifices to preserve.

NATO Secretary General on his first day at the new NATO HQ

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NATO's Effective Multilateralism: the means to counter hybrid threats

Maria Elena Argano

Maria Elena Argano was born in Palermo. After a Bachelor's degree in Political Science and International Relations at the University of Palermo, she continued her studies in Brussels. In September 2015, she obtained a Master's in Political Science and International Relations, focusing on peace, security and conflict, at the Université Libre de Bruxelles. A month later, she joined the Mediterranean Institute for International Studies (IMESI) as a volunteer researcher based in Brussels. In January 2016, she started an internship at the NGO EU-Logos Athena (in Brussels) as a policy analyst, in charge of the external relations portfolio and, more specifically, EU-NATO relations. She is currently off-site coordinator of the department dealing with foreign policy, security and defence at the IMESI, and still a policy analyst at EU-Logos.

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On 6th March 2017, NATO Deputy Secretary General Rose Gottemoeller, during her speech at the British think tank Chatham House, underlined the importance of NATO's *effective multilateralism*, namely its ability to interact with other international actors in order to solve the new challenges arising from a multilateral order established after the end of the Second World War.¹ On 18th January 2018, NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg, during his speech to the Parliament of the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia,² stated that resilience and dialogue with other organizations are the main features of NATO's approach.³ First, in this article, a definition of *effective multilateralism* and its theoretical basis in neoliberal institutionalism as elaborated by Robert Keohane and Joseph Nye will be provided. Second, NATO's resilience capabilities and, in this specific case, cooperation with the European Union (EU) for countering hybrid threats will be presented. Finally, considering the last NATO Summit in Warsaw, the *Common Set* and the new structural measures adopted, NATO's examples of cooperation and resilience will be illustrated, in order to show that NATO, with particular reference to countering hybrid threats, thanks to *effective multilateralism*, is able to include the EU within its policies and, at the same time, succeed in improving its resilience, considered as the ability to adapt to new challenges and improve its capabilities to react to threats.

1. Effective multilateralism: definition and theory

On 6th March 2017, during a conference at Chatham House about NATO's capabilities to meet changing security challenges, NATO Deputy Secretary General Rose Gottemoeller gave a speech, in which she wanted to stress that current global problems require multilateral answers, based on decisions agreed among several regional actors. This is why adaptability has been one of NATO's paramount aims: every multilateral organization has to adapt to changing circumstances if it does not want to fail. After the fall of the Berlin Wall, NATO had to adapt to a changing world, focusing on collective defence and cooperation with the EU, with which, in recent years, the Allies pursued an increasingly structured cooperation. Indeed, today, the two organizations, although structurally different, have agreed, in the name of multilateralism, on forty proposals in several key sectors, including the management of hybrid and cyber threats, the capacity of their respective partners, and internal security. Furthermore, according to the Deputy Secretary General, the increase in NATO-EU cooperation is important because it involves mutual reinforcement.⁴

1) NATO Website, *Effective multilateralism: how NATO adapts to meet changing security challenges*: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/opinions_142021.htm?selectedLocale=en, (06/03/2017)

2) Turkey recognises the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia with its constitutional name.

3) NATO Website, *Speech by NATO Secretary General*: https://www.nato.int/cps/ua/natohq/opinions_150855.htm (18/01/2018)

4) NATO Website, *Effective multilateralism: how NATO adapts to meet changing security challenges*: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/opinions_142021.htm?selectedLocale=en (06/03/2017)

Remarks by NATO Deputy Secretary General Rose Gottemoeller

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Actually, the concept of *effective multilateralism* is neither historically nor theoretically connected to NATO's approach, but has become so over time. The approach based on *effective multilateralism* first appeared in the 2003 European Security Strategy, and referred specifically to the development of international organizations, regimes and treaties to improve effectiveness in countering threats to peace, ensuring international security, and promoting the rule of law. Thus, according to the 2003 definition, the way to pursue international security was based on multilateral cooperation between organizations and through partnerships with key actors.⁵ The theory behind this approach is the concept of

"complex interdependence" drawn up in 1977 by Joseph Nye and Robert Keohane, political scientists and founders of the theory of neoliberal institutionalism in international relations. Robert Keohane, in his essay *International Institutions and State Power*, states that the concept of cooperation has to be understood as a series of measures taken by individuals, states, and organizations whose dependability is determined through coordination. This means that when several actors cooperate, they change their behaviour and renounce part of their interests in order to comply with the other's behaviour.⁶ This type of relationship, based on a cost-benefit analysis, is a form of *effective multilateralism*. Different organizations which interact

5) *European Security Strategy*: <https://europa.eu/globalstrategy/fr/node/13> (12/12/2003)

6) KEOHANE, Robert, (1989), *International Institutions and State power*, Westview Press, , p. 167

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with each other thus develop their strategic communication, their approaches, their preferences, and sometimes their internal structures, in order to cooperate and achieve optimal results, adapted to the existing international scenario, and at the same time emphasizing the importance of resilience. From a practical point of view, it is the same approach emphasized by the NATO Deputy Secretary General, who referred precisely to NATO's adaptation capabilities, and in particular with the EU, to counter threats, including hybrid ones.

2. Countering hybrid threats

Hybrid threats are often referred to in the context of the ongoing conflict in Ukraine (after the annexation of Crimea), and the advance of the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria since 2013. Actually, concerns over hybrid threats were initially presented in NATO's 2010 *Strategic Concept* and incorporated into the *NATO Capstone Concept*, which defined hybrid threats as "those posed by adversaries, with the ability to simultaneously employ conventional and non-conventional means adaptively in pursuit of their objectives".⁷ Therefore, the term "hybrid threats" has an elastic but complex meaning that highlights the difficulty in countering them. This is why the term is often used to refer to hybrid war, merging new threats with ethnic conflicts, terrorism, migration and weak institutions that cause internal crises. Changing the type of challenges also changes the actors involved, who are no longer just two armies belonging to two states, but can be regular or irregular forces, or criminal groups using unconventional means, such as technology.⁸ For the Alliance, this means not only using of a multilateral approach, but also the increase of resilience.

Jamie Shea, NATO's Deputy Assistant Secretary General for Emerging Security Challenges, in his essay "Resilience: a core element of collective defense", stated that resilience is a constant priority for NATO and its member states, because adapting to new threats, especially hybrid ones, has an impact on collective security.⁹ According to him, NATO, over the past two years, has improved its intelligence and early warning sharing processes to better anticipate and map hybrid threats, and improve resilience. The principle of resilience is mentioned in Article 3 of the North Atlantic Treaty: "In order to achieve the objectives of this Treaty, the Parties, separately and jointly, by means of

continuous and effective self-help and mutual aid, will maintain and develop their individual and collective capacity to resist armed attack".¹⁰ This means that each NATO member state must be sufficiently sturdy and adaptable to support the full spectrum of crises foreseen by the Alliance. So, it is precisely in the name of *effective multilateralism* that cooperation with the private sector, and with the EU, can strengthen the efficiency and effectiveness of NATO measures at all levels.¹¹ In this sense, the principle of resilience is linked to *effective multilateralism*. Indeed, according to Jamie Shea, the relationship between NATO and the EU is an example of a joint approach based on shared awareness and coordination in countering hybrid threats. NATO and the EU are continuing to cooperate at the regulatory level, precisely because of the structural differences, meaning that the two organizations define their own strategies and, at the same time, try to harmonize procedures and support mutual efforts.¹²

On 2nd May 2017, the Supreme Allied Commander Transformation (Norfolk - United States) hosted leaders from 34 NATO and EU member countries, as well as private sector actors, during a conference entitled "Interdependency in Resilience". The aim was to improve the understanding and visibility of resilience in the security sector and explain why, today, a dialogue is needed between different actors in order to build and improve NATO's resilience: this requires a permanent interconnection between the civil, private and military sectors. Again, the Alliance has shown that dialogue and interdependence with the EU are at the heart of its approach to countering hybrid threats.¹³

Guillaume Lasconjarias and Andreas Jacobs, in their essay "NATO's Hybrid Flanks: handling unconventional warfare in the South and the East"¹⁴, state that NATO has already begun the process of adapting its strategies and its structures for the security of the Alliance, as confirmed by NATO's resilience to the threats from its southern and eastern borders. Indeed, according to the two authors, two events stimulated the Alliance to adapt its structures and recognize the importance of the hybrid security threat: the outbreak of the Syrian crisis and the advance of Islamic state, and the annexation of Crimea

7) NATO Website, *Strategic Concept 2010*: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_82705.htm (19/11/2010)

8) NATO Website, *Strategic Concept 2010*: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_82705.htm (19/11/2010)

9) SHEA, Jamie, *Resilience: a core element of collective defense*, NATO Review Magazine, <https://www.nato.int/docu/review/2016/Also-in-2016/nato-defence-cyber-resilience/EN/index.htm> (30/03/2016)

10) NATO Website, *The North Atlantic Treaty*: https://www.nato.int/cps/ic/natohq/official_texts_17120.htm (04/04/1949)

11) NATO Website, *Resilience and Article 3*: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_132722.htm (22/06/2016)

12) SHEA, Jamie, *Resilience: a core element of collective defense*, NATO Review Magazine: <https://www.nato.int/docu/review/2016/Also-in-2016/nato-defence-cyber-resilience/EN/index.htm> (30/03/2016)

13) *Building Resilience: collaborative proposals to help nations and partners*: <http://www.act.nato.int/images/stories/events/2017/resilience/resilience-wp.pdf> (04/05/2017)

14) Guillaume Lasconjarias and Jeffrey A. Larsen (2015), *NATO's Response to Hybrid Threats*, NATO Defense College Forum Papers Series, p. 255

Raimonds Vejonis (President, Latvia), King Philippe of Belgium (King of the Belgians), NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg, Donald Trump (President, United States), Kolinda Grabar-Kitarovic (President, Croatia) and Mark Rutte (Prime Minister, the Netherlands)

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nato/34504611980/in/album-72157681182468244/>

by Russia. In 2015, NATO's Readiness Action Plan (RAP) had shown that the best way to counter hybrid threats was to adopt a comprehensive approach based on the interaction between different actors at different levels.¹⁵ This is why in 2016, NATO started to cooperate systematically with the EU, to counter hybrid threats that represented a danger to the security of both institutions, founding their relationship on *effective multilateralism*.

In several cases, NATO tried to adopt an approach based on *effective multilateralism*, as a channel to promote resilience. The first case dates back to 11th February 2016, when NATO Defence Ministers decided to deploy ships to the Aegean to support Greece and Turkey, and to cooperate with the EU Frontex border agency to tackle illegal immigration. Indeed, the Alliance is still monitoring Greece and Turkey's territorial waters, providing information to their coastguards and supporting international efforts in the fight against illegal migration.

In addition, a few months later, NATO agreed to extend its engagement by supporting the EU's Operation Sophia in the central Mediterranean, providing operational, logistical and informational support. Afghanistan is another example that highlights NATO's ability to adapt and cooperate with the EU. Indeed, when the EUPOL Operation was launched in 2007 to provide funding for civilian projects, NATO played a key role. Cooperation between the EU and NATO also continued after the end of the International Security Assistance Force mission (ISAF - 2014) and the launch of a subsequent mission to train, assist and advise Afghan forces. In addition, until 2016, NATO naval forces were deployed with EU naval forces (Operation Atalanta) off the coast of Somalia, to fight against piracy.¹⁶ This shows that NATO is able to involve other actors to counter hybrid threats, thus achieving a double aim: cooperation with other actors, such as the EU, to provide operational support; and increasing its adaptability, and hence its resilience to hybrid threats.

¹⁵ *Ibid*, p. 258

¹⁶ NATO Website, *Relations with the European Union*: [https://www.nato.int/cps/ua/natohq/topics_49217.htm# \(13/02/2018\)](https://www.nato.int/cps/ua/natohq/topics_49217.htm# (13/02/2018))

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NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg speaking at the Warsaw Summit

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/nato/27578382463>

3. Effective multilateralism with the EU from Warsaw

NATO's ability to adapt to new threats, especially hybrid ones, is not only linked to a concept developed by experts or to international relations' theories. Resilience, understood as the ability to evolve, change and cope with new challenges, is concretely traceable within the policies that the Alliance intends to adopt, including the development of a multilateral approach.

In July 2016, during the Warsaw Summit, the Alliance dealt with the issue of hybrid threats. In the *Communiqué* published after the meeting of the 28 Heads of State and Government, NATO announced the adoption of measures to effectively deal with the challenges posed by hybrid threats. In this sense, the Alliance presented itself as an organization able to assist its member states by adopting a multilateral approach based on effective coordination with relevant international partners and organizations, and in particular with the EU in

its efforts to counter hybrid war.¹⁷ Furthermore, NATO showed its commitment to strengthen resilience by developing its capabilities both as a state-based organization and as an international actor. Indeed, during the Warsaw Summit, the Allies issued the "Commitment to enhance resilience" in which they set out their goal of maintaining and further developing individual and collective capabilities to resist any form of armed attack, and resilience appears to be at the heart of the Alliance's approach to a wider and evolving range of military and non-military security challenges.¹⁸ In this project, the EU wanted to contribute to strengthening resilience and enhance the Alliance's ability to counter hybrid threats, working jointly on analysis and prevention through information and intelligence sharing.¹⁹

17) NATO Website, Warsaw Summit Communiqué, art. 72: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_133169.htm#hybrid (09/07/2016)

18) NATO Website, Commitment to enhance resilience: https://www.nato.int/cps/su/natohq/official_texts_133180.htm (08/07/2016)

19) Consilium Website, Joint Declaration: <http://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/21481/nato-eu-declaration-8-july-en-final.pdf> (08/07/2016)

On 25th May 2017, in their meeting in Brussels, the Allies agreed on an action plan to do more in the international fight against terrorism. The plan involved improving the performance of Airborne Warning and Control Systems (AWACS), and stepping up information sharing. Moreover, NATO confirmed its adherence to the International Coalition to defeat ISIL and the establishment of a new terrorism intelligence cell at NATO Headquarters in Brussels, as well as the appointment of a coordinator to oversee the efforts of the Alliance.²⁰ A few months later, on 2nd October 2017, NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg, together with High Representative of the European Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy Federica Mogherini, attended the inauguration of the Centre of Excellence for countering hybrid threats (Hybrid CoE), created upon the initiative of the Finnish government and supported by both the EU and NATO, in Helsinki. One of the CoE's aims is to support the activities of participating countries, the EU and NATO, and at the same time create and develop interoperability between the two organizations.²¹ In fact, during the inauguration speech, the NATO Secretary General affirmed that the aim was to work in close cooperation with the EU, precisely to improve the results of countering hybrid threats.²² Again, the Alliance has proven its resilience and improved its relations with the EU by promoting *effective multilateralism*.

Finally, on 5th December 2017, the "Common Set of new proposals" was presented by the two organizations in order to put into practice the relationship already established in Warsaw in 2016. Sure enough, both the EU and NATO intend to intensify their relations by developing multidimensional approaches in order to share information and intensify cooperation within the CoE for countering hybrid threats, with a particular focus on threats from the East and South. In this sense, for both organizations, strategic communications play a key role in the systematic exchange of practices and information, enabling NATO to develop its own resilience.²³

Despite its origins as a European security strategy, it seems that *effective multilateralism* is now a NATO core value for countering hybrid threats. Just as Robert Keohane states in his theories, the Alliance is an organization like any other, that needs to adapt to the existing scenario to survive, and at the same time involve other actors, such as the EU, in the detection of certain hybrid-like threats. As quoted by NATO's Deputy Secretary General in

her speech on 6th March 2017, the Alliance began a process based on cooperation with various public and private actors in order to achieve its goals. *Effective multilateralism*, in this case, could be considered a rational choice providing a dual result. Including new actors and involving them in its policies (and adapting to their preferences by reaching agreements) helps the Alliance to increase its ability to adapt to new international challenges by following a multidimensional approach. Thanks to multilateralism, it is able to increase its resilience in countering threats, giving and receiving support from other actors who share the same perception of the challenges, in order to maintain peace and security.

20) NATO Website, Countering terrorism https://www.nato.int/cps/ua/natohq/topics_77646.htm (19/12/2017)

21) Hybrid CoE Website, About Us: <https://www.hybridcoe.fi/about-us/> (24/04/2018)

22) NATO Website, Remarks: https://www.nato.int/cps/ic/natohq/opinions_147499.htm (02/10/2017)

23) NATO Website, Common Set of new proposals: https://www.nato.int/cps/ic/natohq/official_texts_149522.htm?selectedLocale=en (05/12/2017)

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Senior Course 132

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ARMENIA
First Secr. V. AFYAN

BELGIUM
COL F. VANDENBUSSCHE

BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA
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Our Courses

GFOAC 2018/1

From 11 to 15 June 2018, the *Generals, Flag Officers and Ambassadors' Course (GFOAC 2018-1)* took place at the NATO Defense College. GFOAC 2018-1, entitled "NATO: leading up to the 2018 Brussels Summit", was attended by 44 senior civilian and military participants from NATO and Partner countries.

GFOAC is a high-level course aimed at one- to three-star officers and civilians of equivalent rank from the member countries of NATO, the Partnership for Peace, the Mediterranean Dialogue, the Istanbul Cooperation Initiative and Global Partners. The course seeks to promote shared understanding of contemporary security challenges and NATO's interests and capabilities.

Modular Short Course 132-1

Our Courses

Modular Short Courses form part of the five-month Senior Course. Since the Senior Course is divided into several Study Periods on specific themes, these can be attended by military officers and civilian officials who are not able to join the Senior Course for its entire duration. To make this possible, the NDC offers five Short Modular Courses during every Senior Course: each MSC is designed to provide participants with an opportunity to update and improve their knowledge of key political, military, defence-related, economic and socio-cultural questions with implications for the Alliance.

Our Courses

The Integrated Partner Orientation Course (IPOC 2018/1) on “NATO Present and Future” was held at the College from 16 to 20 April 2018, in conjunction with Senior Course 132 and Modular Short Course 132-3. This edition brought together 17 participants from 11 Partner countries. The Course is designed to analyse the nature of NATO as an organization, examining its activities and policies, as well as its contribution to the field of security. Within this framework, it was possible to focus on the changing nature of the security environment and the relevant steps and adaptations NATO must undertake over the next few years.

From 7 to 11 May 2018, the seventh Senior Executive Regional Conference (SERC 7) was held at the NATO Defense College, with the participation of 29 ambassadors, generals and senior officers and officials from 17 NATO and Partner countries.

The aim of this five-day conference is to promote mutual understanding on issues related to the Mediterranean and the Gulf, to enhance knowledge of current security challenges to the Alliance and its partners, and to allow participants to familiarize themselves with current and prospective issues facing NATO.

World News

<https://voiceofpeopletoday.com/special-project-dubbed-russia-house-open-davos-world-economic-forum/>

23/01/2018

World Economic Forum held in Davos, Switzerland

More than 3,000 leaders from over 100 countries came together to focus on finding ways to reaffirm international cooperation on crucial shared interests, such as the environment, the global economy and international security, in the spirit of the theme of the 48th Annual Meeting, "Creating a Shared Future in a Fractured World".

<https://erc.europa.eu/event/world-economic-forum-annual-meeting-2018>

31/01/2018

UN Special Envoy Angelina Jolie visits NATO Headquarters

In a joint meeting of the North Atlantic Council and the Military Committee, Ms Jolie and Allied representatives focused on NATO's efforts to prevent sexual and gender-based violence, and discussed what more the Alliance will do.

https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/news_151259.htm?selectedLocale=en

15/02/2018

NATO Defence Ministers take decisions to strengthen the Alliance

NATO Defence Ministers wrapped up two days of talks in Brussels, focused on the NATO Command Structure, fair burden-sharing and the Alliance's efforts to project stability beyond its borders. Ministers took stock of progress in implementing NATO's Defence Investment Pledge. By 2024, 15 Allies are expected to spend 2% of their GDP or more on defence.

https://www.nato.int/cps/su/natohq/news_152125.htm?selectedLocale=en

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World News

17/02/2018

NATO Secretary General meets leaders at the Munich Security Conference

NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg discussed the security challenges facing the Alliance in a series of bilateral meetings at the Munich Security Conference. Mr Stoltenberg also addressed the Munich Security Conference and delivered a keynote speech at a gathering organized by the Bundesverband der Deutschen Industrie (BDI).

(https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/news_152168.htm?selectedLocale=en)

04/03/2018

Facebook—Cambridge Analytica scandal

The collected data was allegedly used to attempt to influence voter opinion on behalf of politicians who hired them. The scandal was significant for inciting public discussion on ethical standards for social media companies, political consulting organizations, and politicians. Consumer advocates called for greater consumer protection in online media and the right to privacy, as well as curbs on misinformation and propaganda.

(<https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2018/mar/22/cambridge-analytica-scandal-the-biggest-revelations-so-far>)

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/bookcatalog/27162721118/>

19/03/2018

Joint press point with NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg and UK Foreign Secretary Boris Johnson

“We stand in solidarity with the United Kingdom and the UK is not alone, we are responding as an Alliance.” With these words, Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg strongly condemned the recent attack in Salisbury, and took a stand against such terrible events while reaffirming the Alliance’s support and solidarity towards the United Kingdom.

(https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/opinions_153049.htm)

World News

<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:WMD-chemical2.svg>

07/04/2018

Syria chemical attack: weapons inspectors to investigate site

A chemical attack in the Syrian city of Douma reportedly killed at least 70 people. On-site medics said a mixture of chlorine gas and sarin was used in the attack. According to rebel forces in Douma, non-governmental aid and medical workers there, and a number of countries, including the United States, most NATO members, and the European Union, the attack was carried out by the Syrian Army.

(<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2018/apr/13/chemical-weapons-inspectors-to-investigate-syria-attack-site>)

20/04/2018

North Korea—South Korea historic summit

North Korean leader Kim Jong Un and South Korean President Moon Jae-in held a historic summit, potentially setting aside decades of animosity and paving the way for a peace deal that would have been unimaginable even a few months ago.

(<https://www.vox.com/2018/4/27/17290344/north-korea-south-korea-kim-jong-un-moon-trump>)

09/05/2018

USA withdraws from the Iranian Nuclear Deal

President Donald Trump announced on 9th May that he is withdrawing from the Iran nuclear deal, pitting him against the United States' closest allies and leaving the future of Tehran's nuclear ambitions in question.

"It is clear to me that we cannot prevent an Iranian nuclear bomb under the decaying and rotten structure of the current agreement."

(<https://edition.cnn.com/2018/05/08/politics/donald-trump-iran-deal-announcement-decision/index.html>)

<http://www.europe1.fr/international/donald-trump-annonce-le-retrait-des-etats-unis-de-laccord-sur-le-nucleaire-iranien-3647003>

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World News

<https://www.flickr.com/photos/zeevveez/28183625558>

14/05/2018

Opening of the US Embassy in Jerusalem

On May 14, 1948, as the Jews of Palestine declared the establishment of a Jewish state called Israel, US President Harry Truman granted immediate recognition on behalf of the United States, becoming the first head of state to do so. On May 14, 2018, 70 years later, by decision of President Donald Trump, the U.S. Embassy moved to Jerusalem from Tel Aviv, where it had been since 1966.

<https://abcnews.go.com/International/opening-us-embassy-jerusalem/story?id=55009442>

09/06/2018

G7 summit: Donald Trump lashes out at America's key allies

US President Donald Trump has renewed his attacks on America's closest allies following the divisive G7 summit in Canada. During a news conference, Mr Trudeau reasserted his opposition to US tariffs on steel and aluminium, and vowed to press ahead with retaliatory moves on 1 July.

<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-us-canada-44434558>

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:G7_Working_Lunch_in_Canada_-_2018.jpg

25/06/2018

Secretary General welcomes stronger NATO-EU cooperation

NATO Secretary General Jens Stoltenberg welcomed strengthened cooperation between the EU and NATO ahead of a meeting with EU Defence Ministers on Monday (25 June 2018). The Secretary General noted that he will sign a new Joint Declaration with the Presidents of the European Council and the European Commission at the NATO Summit, setting out a shared vision for further cooperation.

https://www.nato.int/cps/su/natohq/news_156263.htm?selectedLocale=en

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Amr YOSSEF and Christopher D. YUNG
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Edited by Beatrice Heuser, Tormod Heier and Guillaume Lasconjarias

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Karl-Heinz KAMP

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